

of two moles of *o*- or *m*-phenylenediamine and two mole of benzil or acetylacetone, is coordinated. The molar conductance measured in different solvents gives the required values for 1 : 2 electrolyte, thus suggesting that the anions are not coordinated as indicated in the formulae of the complexes.

In the ir spectra of the complexes, the NH₂ and CO stretching frequencies are absent and in their place a sharp band appears at 1 620 cm⁻¹ due to azomethine stretch and which suggests that Schiff base condensation with the consequent formation of macrocycle has occurred. The negative shift in its frequency by 20 cm⁻¹ or more is due to its coordination to zirconyl ion^{6,8}. This coordination is further supported by a sharp band at 430 ± 10 cm⁻¹ which has been assigned to (Zr←N) stretch⁶, and the Zr=O stretch is observed as a strong band at 970 ± 10 cm⁻¹ as found in other similar complexes⁷. The absorptions associated with anions in these complexes are identified at 1 085 and 620 cm⁻¹ for perchlorate⁹, 1 050 and 650 cm⁻¹ for tetrafluoroborate⁹, 1 360 and 810 cm⁻¹ for nitrate¹⁰, 1 640, 1 350, 890 and 770 cm⁻¹ for oxalate¹¹, 2 053, 745 and 484 cm⁻¹ for thiocyanate¹² and 570 cm⁻¹ for chloride¹³ and all these correspond to their uncoordinated nature.

In the ¹H nmr spectra of free ligands, multiplets are observed in the region δ 7.2–7.6 due to phenyl protons, while in ligand L₂ the CH₂ and CH₃ protons appear as singlet at δ 1.9 and 2.6, respectively. In the ¹H nmr spectra of the complex [ZrOL₁](ClO₄)₂, a single broad band appears at δ 7.4, while in the complex [ZrO(L₂)](ClO₄)₂, the CH₂ and CH₃ protons are seen at δ 2.1 and 2.9, respectively, and the multiplet corresponding to the phenyl protons appear at δ 7.6 and 7.8. This slight shift in the positions of these signals and the slight overlapping of the phenyl protons are due to the coordination from the adjacent nitrogen.

It is thus suggested that the ligands L₁ and L₂ completely encircle the oxo-ions through their four azomethine nitrogens and planar closed ring structures (1, 2) result. The oxygen atom of the ZrO moiety occupied the axial position projecting outside the planar macrocyclic plane. The coordination of anions will result in consequent ring opening with less stable structure and hence these are not coordinated.

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Rhenium(IV) Complexes with Pyrazole and Substituted-pyrazoles

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In this paper we report rhenium(IV) complexes of the type Re₂O₂Cl₂L₂, where L = pyrazole (Pz), 3-methylpyrazole (MePz), 3,5-dimethylpyrazole (DmPz), 3,4,5-trimethylpyrazole (TmPz) and 1,3,4,5-tetramethylpyrazole (TetmPz).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. 3-Methylpyrazole was obtained by decarboxylation of 3-methyl-5-carboxylic acid. While dimethylpyrazole was obtained by condensing acetyl acetone with hydrazine, tri- and tetra-methylpyrazoles were obtained by condensing 3-methyl acetyl acetone with hydrazine and methyl hydrazine respectively¹. The compounds were purified by fractional distillation. Potassium hexachlororhenate(IV) was prepared by the reduction of potassium

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF RHENIUM(IV) COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} B.M.
		Re	N	Cl		
$\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{Pa})_4$	Dark brown	44.12 (48.89)	18.15 (18.30)	20.28 (20.27)	828.4 (818.4)	0.67
$\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{MePa})_4$	Light brown	42.09 (41.17)	12.42 (12.38)	19.14 (19.01)	880.6 (874.4)	0.78
$\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{DmPa})_4$	Brown	38.72 (38.77)	11.85 (11.66)	18.01 (17.90)	941.2 (930.4)	0.71
$\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{TmPa})_4$	Brown	36.51 (36.84)	11.19 (11.02)	16.87 (16.92)	980.1 (986.4)	0.69
$\text{Re}_2\text{O}_7\text{Cl}_4(\text{TeTmPa})_4$	Deep brown	34.28 (34.72)	10.60 (10.44)	16.17 (16.04)	1055 (1042.4)	0.75

perrhenate with potassium iodide in concentrated hydrochloric acid medium⁸.

Preparation of complexes: An aqueous solution of potassium hexachlororhenate (0.005 mol) was mixed with an aqueous ethanolic solution of the Me-pyrazoles (0.040 mol) and warmed. The resulting deep chocolate coloured solution on concentration at room temperature gave brown-dark brown crystals, which were washed with cold methanol and petroleum ether and dried over fused calcium chloride. The complexes were further recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether. The compounds were soluble in all common organic solvents like methanol and acetone, but insoluble in water and petroleum ether. Elemental analyses data are presented in Table I.

Room temperature (298 K) magnetic moment (μ_{eff}), molar conductance (Λ_M) in methanol, electronic spectra (methanol) and ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded and their molecular weights in chloroform were determined by ebullioscopic method.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis data (Table 1) correspond to the general formula ReOCl_2L_2 for the complexes. Molecular weight data indicate the complexes to be dimeric. Low molar conductance ($10-15 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) values of the complexes show their non-electrolytic nature. The electronic spectra of the complexes gave two bands at 27 400 and 16 500 cm^{-1} corresponding to the transitions ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ respectively suggesting rhenium(IV) in a typical octahedral environment⁹. The ν_{NH} bands in the ir spectra of the complexes were somewhat diffused and the ring vibrations were lowered due to complex formation⁶. A strong band around 897-910 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{Re=O}}$ was observed in all the complexes⁵⁻⁸. Another strong band around 305-310 cm^{-1} was due to $\nu_{\text{Re-Cl}}$ ⁹. The μ_{eff} values of the complexes were unusually low (0.65-0.75 B.M.) for rhenium(IV) ion with three unpaired electrons⁴⁻⁶. The lowering may be due to chloride-bridged (A) or oxobridged (B) binuclear structure of these complexes.

The presence of $\nu_{\text{Re=O}}$ band in the ir spectra of the complexes suggests the chloride-bridged structure (A) more plausible for these complexes.

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Beryllium(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of Methyl 2-Phenylazo-3-oxobutanoate

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[N continuation of our studies on 2-arylozo-1,3-dicarbonyls and their metal complexes¹⁻⁴, we report the synthesis and characterisation of the Be^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of methyl 2-phenylazo-3-oxobutanoate (phenylazomethylacetate, HL).